

THE ROLE OF SCHOOL MANAGEMENT IN ENHANCEMENT OF FOREIGN LANGUAGE EDUCATION

Yoqubova Umida Urol qizi

Tashkent State Pedagogical University,
2nd year master's degree in management of educational institutions.

E mail: umiyoqubova.3003@gmail.com

Phone number: +998998709803

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Abstract. *Improving foreign language teaching at school is an important political and social task in today's globalized world. The transition to the competence paradigm requires mastery of new methodology, curriculum development and assessment methods. This article discusses the peculiarities of the implementation of the new state educational standards (SES) in the context of teaching foreign languages in Uzbekistan. The purpose of the article is to present the author's concept of achieving the requirements of the standards in foreign language teaching. The article begins by highlighting the reasons for prioritizing foreign language proficiency at the school level and assesses the situation with foreign language teaching in Uzbekistan. Next, the traditional roles of teachers in the teacher-centered classroom are considered, which negatively affects the development of students' personality. Then the article presents key innovative multifaceted roles of a foreign language teacher. The conceptual approach emphasizes the prerequisites for the development of a new socio-educational environment and provides teachers with practical recommendations for the successful implementation of the requirements of the State Educational Standards in foreign language teaching.*

Keywords: *competence approach, foreign language teaching, teacher's roles, education management.*

РОЛЬ ШКОЛЬНОГО МЕНЕДЖМЕНТА В РАЗВИТИИ ИНОСТРАННОЯЗЫЧНОГО ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ

Аннотация. *Совершенствование преподавания иностранного языка в школе является важной политической и социальной задачей в современном глобализированном мире. Переход к компетентностной парадигме требует овладения новой методологией, разработкой учебных программ и методами оценки. В данной статье рассматриваются особенности реализации новых государственных образовательных стандартов (ГОС) в условиях преподавания иностранных языков в Узбекистане. Цель статьи – представить авторскую концепцию достижения требований стандартов обучения иностранному языку. Статья начинается с выделения причин приоритета владения иностранным языком на уровне школы и оценки ситуации с преподаванием иностранного языка в Узбекистане. Далее рассматриваются традиционные роли учителя на недорегулированном занятии, что негативно влияет на развитие личности учащихся. Далее в статье представлены ключевые инновационные многогранные роли преподавателя иностранного языка. Концептуальный подход подчеркивает предпосылки развития новой социально-образовательной среды и дает педагогам практические рекомендации для успешной реализации требований Государственного образовательного стандарта при обучении иностранному языку.*

Ключевые слова: компетентностный подход, обучение иностранному языку, роль учителя, управление образованием.

The development of information technology has led to significant changes in the global economy and social life. The education system must respond to these changes in order to be sure that the young generation is well prepared to work and live in new conditions. Modern reforming of the education system in Uzbekistan is mainly determined by the world trends in pedagogical sciences, the basis of which is the transition from knowledge-oriented teaching practices to more practical methodology aimed at the development of competencies as the ultimate goal of any learning, including foreign language learning. Today, the management of educational institutions, as well as foreign language teachers in Uzbekistan, must build their curricula in accordance with the academic achievements laid down in the new State Educational Standards (SES). It is the competency-based approach that lies at the heart of the SES, which define the foreign language curriculum as a set of competencies. However, the implementation of the SES faces many difficulties, one of which is related to the fact that teachers at all levels are not fully aware of the new concepts embedded in the standards. In this regard, different stakeholders have disparate views on both the theory and practice of competency-based approach in foreign language teaching. The main assumption is that the successful implementation of the new approach and the Standards depends on the competence of teachers.

In reality, the average high school graduate still has enormous difficulties in using a foreign language or any other national languages of Uzbekistan at the threshold level. This is unacceptable in the era of economic globalization and the expansion of international economic ties that involve learning and working in a foreign-language environment. Of course, it is easy to blame school teachers for their insufficient language skills. However, it is not really their fault. First, educational administrators have paid little or no attention to second language instruction. This neglect can be easily found in the following examples:

- Secondary schools allocate only 2 hours per week for learning a second language;
- Languages are taught in the absence of a language environment;
- Communicative activities of schoolchildren are scarce, preference is given mainly to writing or reading, and occasionally to pair work;
- The teaching process is irregular, vacations and other long breaks have a negative impact on the acquisition of a second language;
- The heads of most educational institutions do not themselves speak a foreign language and are not familiar with modern methods of language education management;
- Material and technical.

These educational objectives require a fundamentally new approach to foreign language teaching, as it is impossible to achieve them only with the help of foreign language teachers who meet with students 3-4 times a week. Therefore, it is imperative to instill in school and educational administrators the skills and knowledge of foreign language teaching at the present stage. Innovations and improvement of foreign language education at school are related to educational reforms in Uzbekistan. The reforms includes six main directions of education development. These directions are:

- 1) introduction of new educational standards;
- 2) creation of a network of advanced search and support for gifted children with subsequent monitoring of these children during their formative years;
- 3) launch of regular projects aimed at improving the qualification and renewal of pedagogical staff and a system for encouraging the most effective specialists in this field;
- 4) new recommendations on the work, design, construction and material and technical support of schools. The main criterion is the high level and feeling of comfort in schools.
- 5) Individual attention to each pupil, which allows minimizing health risks in the learning process;
- 6) Increased autonomy of schools.

Certainly, the new standards require a different organization of children's activities and the development of their language skills. Unfortunately, the teacher-centered practice is still prevailing, with the teacher playing the leading role, i.e. when the student is encouraged by the teacher to study the subject. As a result, the student becomes a passive object of learning. This is the main characteristic of the old scholastic education, which does not develop leadership qualities and does not make the student an active subject of learning. Today this model is seriously criticized both in Uzbek and world pedagogy. The main reason for criticism is the reproductive nature of education and inequality between its participants, the student is only a passive recipient of knowledge. The ultimate goal of this approach is to transfer to the student complete and substantive knowledge of the issues under discussion, as well as to assimilate all the information communicated by the teacher in the necessary volume. This approach forces the student to formulate their answers without distorting or altering the original meaning. As a result, the traditional model produces students who have deep knowledge in various subject areas but are not always able to adapt to real life and socio-economic challenges. In addition, this model deprives students of autonomy and personal responsibility for their academic achievements or failures. This lack of learning autonomy has a destructive effect on students' learning activities.

In this regard, one of the main tasks facing the school administration is to create a foreign-language environment. Since regular Uzbek schools lack both native speakers and management staff with foreign language skills, it is quite difficult to achieve this goal. The system of extracurricular activities aimed at developing foreign language skills is particularly difficult. The experience of successful schools shows that the lack of foreign-language environment is effectively compensated by organizing theaters in foreign languages, song and essay contests, watching famous Uzbek cartoons dubbed into a foreign language, pen pal clubs or Skype communication with peers speaking the target language, etc. In recent years, school and inter-school summer/winter camps aimed at the development of foreign language communication have proved to be a good practice. Also, in our opinion, schools practicing individual and group tutoring deserve more attention. However, as noted above, the work requires a different, more effective model for managing extracurricular activities. The important components of this model are methodological support for organizers of extracurricular activities aimed at improving the foreign language competence of pedagogical and managerial staff, and the development of a system of material incentives for teachers. At the same time, the transition to the new

management model is quite complicated and requires qualified scientific and methodological support.

Quality teaching is the only central factor in foreign language acquisition, and it, in turn, depends largely on the quality of teacher training and the receptivity of school administrations implementing educational reforms to the demands of educators. In the context of foreign language teaching, a successful school should take into account such key indicators as creating an atmosphere conducive to increasing children's intrinsic motivation to learn a foreign language; fostering students' independence in communicative activities; expanding the sphere of foreign language communication; creating conditions for students to evaluate the results they have achieved in learning a foreign language.

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